

A Tuning Method for the Supplementary Voltage Controller of Dual-Side Grid Forming Converters in Distributed Storage Systems

ANGEL PEREZ-BASANTE ¹, ASIER GIL DE MURO ¹, ANDER ORDONO ², SALVADOR CEBALLOS ^{1,4}, ENEKO UNAMUNO ³, AND JON ANDONI BARRERA ³

¹Tecnalia, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), 48160 Derio, Spain

²Department of Electrical Engineering, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), 20600 Eibar, Spain

³Electrical Energy Group at the Mondragon School of Engineering, Mondragon University (MU), 20500 Mondragon, Spain

⁴Department of Electronic Technology, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), 48013 Bilbao, Spain

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: ANGEL PEREZ-BASANTE (e-mail: angel.perez@tecnalia.com).

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ABSTRACT Utility-scale battery energy storage systems (BESSs) are currently being used to provide auxiliary services, such as frequency regulation, peak shaving, or grid balancing, among others. Hybrid ac/dc distribution grids where the BESS systems are connected in the dc side and the dc/ac interface is implemented through a grid forming (GF) converter are currently researched. These solutions combine the benefits given by the dc distribution and the possibility to provide emulated inertia and damping to the system through the use of GF control techniques. This article presents a novel tuning method, based on small signal analysis, for the configuration parameters of a dual-side GF controller. It aims to minimize the dynamic performance difference between the dual-side and ideal GF controllers, thus ensuring that the dual-side GF provides the expected support to the grid in terms of inertia, damping and primary response, while simultaneously controlling the dc voltage. This is achieved through the optimum tuning of the supplementary dc voltage regulator embedded in the dual-side GF controller. Real-time estimation of the optimum controller gains by making use of an artificial neural network is proposed. Simulation and experimental results are presented to validate the method.

INDEX TERMS Grid forming (GF), virtual synchronous machine (VSM), battery energy storage system (BESS), small signal analysis, hybrid ac/dc distribution grids.

I. INTRODUCTION

The progressive replacement of conventional synchronous generators (SGs) by distributed renewable energy systems, which are connected to the grid through power converters, implies a negative impact in terms of harmonic generation and power system stability [1], [2]. With the aim of mitigating these problems, services are required to be provided by the control techniques of these power converter interfaced resources [1]. Among all of these services, the ability to provide inertia and operate as a voltage source are starting to be widely demanded by grid operators. These features are provided by grid-forming (GF) control techniques [2], [3].

On the other hand, the increasing number of battery energy storage systems (BESSs) integrated in the grid can alleviate

these issues since they can provide the required new services. They are excellent candidates to provide frequency regulation, peak shaving, or grid balancing [4], [5] and specially, inertia and damping emulation services through the use of GF control techniques. The BESS systems can be connected to the ac grid directly through different power converter topologies [4] or making use of dc distribution grids [6]. In the latter case, where a hybrid ac/dc grid is considered (see Fig. 1), several advantages can be obtained from the dc energy transmission, such as no skin or proximity effects, lower cable losses and costs with respect to ac networks, less ac/dc conversion stages or asynchronous grid connection, among others [7]. This hybrid scheme is starting to be considered for instance in fast charging stations with multiple charging points of different

FIGURE 1. Distributed storage system connected to an ac grid through an interface converter that operates in GF mode.

power levels or in public dc distribution grids with multiple distributed charging points, BESS and flexible loads among others. The interface between the ac and dc grids is given by a power converter that can provide GF capabilities [8]. However, besides the auxiliary services, the dc bus voltage must also be regulated. To this end, various dual-side GF control methods have been proposed in the literature. [9] and [10] present dual-side GF controllers designed for modular multilevel converters to enhance stability in hybrid high-voltage ac/dc grids. A similar concept, initially introduced by Zhang et al. [11], is employed in [12] and [13]. These works regulate the dc bus voltage while simultaneously providing emulated inertia and damping characteristics on the ac side. In addition, Bakeer et al. [14] modified the concept from [12] and [13] to also provide inertia to the dc grid [15]. Generally, these methods incorporate an external controller that regulates the dc voltage within the GF structure. However, this external controller also affects the damping and inertia provided to the ac grid. To the best of our knowledge, no research has been conducted to provide guidelines on tuning these external controllers to preserve ac damping and inertia characteristics while regulating the dc voltage using the distributed energy storage capacity on the dc network.

On the other hand, artificial neural networks (ANNs) have been used in the technical literature as part of the modulator [16], [17] or the controller [18] of power electronic converters, being especially useful to tune in real-time the parameters of these controllers [19]. However, this kind of systems has not been used yet to tune the external controller of dual-side GF converters under different ac grid auxiliary service requirements.

This article takes as a basis the dual-side GF concepts presented in [12] and [13] to develop a virtual synchronous machine (VSM) control for the interface converter of the hybrid ac/dc grid represented in Fig. 1. It provides simultaneously GF ac grid auxiliary services (inertia, damping, and primary regulation) and dc voltage regulation through the coordination with different BESS systems connected to the dc grid. The active power reference of the VSM is given by a proportional.integral (PI) supplementary controller that regulates the dc bus voltage without disturbing the VSM conventional dynamic response. The proposed control scheme does not make use of communications between the VSM and

the BESS, unlike other existing control architectures [8]. The main contributions of this article are as follows.

- A method to tune the supplementary controller so that the dual-side VSM provides the required ac-side inertia, damping, and primary regulation while regulating the dc voltage. In addition, the proposed method also tunes the PI settling time to a predefined value. This method is based on a small signal stability analysis where a cost function (CF) is defined to ensure the required VSM performance.
- An ANN that provides the optimum gains of the supplementary controller for the multiple inertia and damping values that can be requested by the power system operator. The ANN is trained with a dataset obtained from the small signal stability analysis.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Section II introduces the GF control method based on BESS distributed systems. The proposed tuning method based on small signal stability analysis is described in Section III. Section IV presents the proposed ANN system to tune the PI parameters under different inertia and damping values. Simulation results are included in Section V. Section VI shows the obtained experimental results that validate the proposed tuning method. Finally, Section VII concludes this article.

II. CONTROL SCHEME FOR DISTRIBUTED STORAGE SYSTEMS

The regulation of the hybrid ac/dc network proposed in this article is achieved through a decentralized control (without communications) between the ac/dc interface converter and the dc/dc converters that connect the BESS systems to the dc grid.

A. GF CONTROL SCHEME FOR THE AC/DC INTERFACE CONVERTER

The GF control makes use of a current-controlled VSM [20], which has been modified with a PI supplementary controller to provide dc voltage regulation. The control scheme is represented in Fig. 2. It contains the following parts.

- 1) Swing equation: The swing equation, given by (1), is implemented with the aim of emulating the electromechanical performance of an SG with specific inertia, H , and damping, K_d , features. This equation uses per unit notation, assuming that the VSM frequency, ω_{VSM} , is close to 1 p.u., approximating the torque by the active power [21]. In addition, the damping term is implemented using the grid frequency calculated by a phase-lock loop, ω_{ext} , as it provides a more accurate emulation of the SG amortisseur winding performance [22]. The rest of the variables included in (1) are the VSM frequency ω_{VSM} , active power P , and active power reference P^*

$$P^* - P = 2H \frac{d\omega_{\text{VSM}}}{dt} + K_d (\omega_{\text{VSM}} - \omega_{\text{ext}}). \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 2. GF control scheme which implements a VSM and additionally regulates the dc bus voltage.

2) Reactive power droop controller: This block provides the primary voltage regulation by means of a Q - V droop controller that regulates the VSM voltage amplitude, as it is given by (2), where Q , Q^* , E_{VSM} , E_{VSM}^* , and K_q are the reactive power, reactive power reference, VSM voltage, VSM voltage reference, and Q - V droop constant, respectively

$$E_{VSM} = E_{VSM}^* + K_q (Q^* - Q). \quad (2)$$

3) Frequency droop controller: In case of grid frequency deviations, the P - f droop controller confers the ability to the power converter to contribute to the primary frequency regulation. This controller is given by (3), where K_w is the f - P droop constant, ω^* is the frequency reference and P_{PI}^* is the active power reference given by the supplementary PI regulator

$$P^* = P_{PI}^* + K_w (\omega^* - \omega_{VSM}). \quad (3)$$

4) Quasistationary SM electrical model: This block is characteristic of a VSM implementation which follows a current-controlled approach. It provides the stator current of an SG in dq-coordinates by making use of a virtual impedance, defined by an inductance L_{VSM} and a resistance R_{VSM} , that emulates the stator windings. In the present work, a quasistationary virtual impedance model has been selected due to its higher stability at low virtual resistance values, providing a higher decoupling between active and reactive powers [20].

5) Current control: The current reference calculated by the SM electrical model is fed to a conventional dq -current controller with feedforward and decoupling terms. The L_f magnitude used in the decoupling terms of the

current controller makes reference to the output filter impedance used to connect the ac/dc interface converter to the ac grid.

6) PI-based dc-voltage supplementary regulator: Previous elements constitute the standard configuration of a current-controlled VSM. In this article, this standard configuration is complemented with a PI supplementary controller that regulates the dc voltage following a similar approach to those in [12] and [13]. In this way, the current-controlled VSM, besides providing GF services to the ac grid, is also able to regulate the dc voltage. The dc voltage reference is provided by the V_{dc} - f droop characteristic described in (4), where $V_{dc,nom}$ is the rated dc voltage, $k_w/K_{droop,dc}$ a combined droop constant, w^* the nominal angular frequency, and w_{VSM} the internal frequency of the VSM provided by the swing (1). It sets the dc voltage reference depending on the value of the internal frequency of the VSM. Note that in the steady state or in sufficiently slow transients, this value approximates to the grid frequency. Section II-B will show how the use of the dc voltage reference obtained from the V_{dc} - f droop in (4), rather than from a fixed value, provides a mechanism to implement primary frequency regulation

$$V_{dc}^* = V_{dc,nom} - \frac{K_w}{K_{droop,dc}} (\omega^* - \omega_{VSM}). \quad (4)$$

B. CONTROL SCHEME FOR THE DC/DC CONVERTERS

The storage systems perform as current sources connected to the dc side of the hybrid ac/dc system. Their active power is modulated according to the V_{dc} - P droop characteristic defined

in (5), where $P_{\text{bat,ref}}$ is the battery power reference, $K_{\text{droop,dc}}$ is the droop constant and V_{dc} is the measured dc bus voltage. Assuming that in the steady state $V_{\text{dc}} = V_{\text{dc}}^*$, (4) can be inserted in (5) providing the combined P - f droop characteristic defined in (6). This mechanism allows to define indirectly a P - f droop that modulates the required active power of the whole system according to the frequency deviation, thus providing primary regulation. Note that the use of the dc voltage as an intermediate variable enables the implementation of this combined droop mechanism without the need of fast communications

$$P_{\text{bat}}^* = P_{\text{bat,ref}} + K_{\text{droop,dc}} (V_{\text{dc}} - V_{\text{dc,nom}}) \quad (5)$$

$$P_{\text{bat}}^* = P_{\text{bat,ref}} - K_w (\omega^* - \omega_{\text{VSM}}). \quad (6)$$

III. PROPOSED TUNING METHOD FOR THE DUAL-SIDE GF CONTROLLER

One of the main challenges to meet in dual-side GF controllers, where the dc bus voltage is also regulated, is the PI controller tuning. A tradeoff between the dc voltage regulation and the VSM dynamic response must be achieved. The tuning method proposed in this section aims to calculate the optimum proportional and integral gains of the supplementary dc controller in such a way that the dynamic response of the dual-side VSM is as close as possible to that of an standard VSM (without supplementary controller) for predefined values of inertia H , damping K_d , and dc voltage settling time T_s .

A. SMALL SIGNAL STABILITY ANALYSIS

The tuning method consists of three different parts, i.e.:

- 1) a small signal stability analysis where the different VSM oscillation modes are studied;
- 2) definition of a CF whose minimization optimizes the PI constants to obtain the desired VSM and dc voltage regulation dynamic responses;
- 3) a real-time tuning system based on ANNs that calculates the optimum PI constants for specific VSM parameters and dc voltage regulation settling time.

A small signal stability analysis is required to tune correctly the PI constants of the supplementary controller. Initially, this analysis is performed considering that the ac/dc interface converter is operated with a standard current-controlled VSM, without the supplementary dc voltage regulator. It will reveal the eigenvalues of the oscillatory modes related to the electromechanical state variables emulated with the VSM. These modes are identified through the participation factors [23], [24] and will be used as target values in the proposed tuning methodology.

Second, the electromechanical eigenvalues of the system shown in Fig. 1, where the ac/dc interface converter is controlled with the whole control scheme depicted in Fig. 2, including the supplementary controller, are calculated. The value of the proportional and integral gains of the controller strongly influence the value of the eigenvalues related to these oscillation modes and consequently the inertia and damping provided by the VSM. This issue is illustrated through the use case described in Table 1. The small signal analysis to obtain

TABLE 1. Use Case Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Nominal power, P	10^6 W	$V_{LL\text{-rms}}$	690 V
Grid SCR and X/R	15 and 29	L_{VSM}	0.25 p.u.
R_{VSM}	0.01 p.u.	L_f	0.15 p.u.
R_f	0.05 p.u.	K_w	20 p.u.
H	10 p.u.	k_d	400 p.u.
Dc bus voltage, V_{dc}	1400 V	Dc bus capacitor, C_{dc}	10.2 mF
Battery voltage, V_{bat}	400 V	$L_{dc/dc}$	0.15 p.u.
$R_{dc/dc}$	0.05 p.u.	$K_{\text{droop-dc}}$	10 p.u.

TABLE 2. Electromechanical Oscillation Modes for Ideal VSM and Dual-Side VSM

Ideal VSM oscillation modes	
Eigenvalue	State variable
-13.398	$\theta_{VSM}, \omega_{VSM}$
-3.55	$\theta_{VSM}, \omega_{VSM}$
Dual-side VSM oscillation modes	
Eigenvalue	State variable
-13.805	$\theta_{VSM}, \omega_{VSM}$
$-1.621 + 2.762i$	$\theta_{VSM}, \omega_{VSM}$
$-1.621 - 2.762i$	$\theta_{VSM}, \omega_{VSM}$

the eigenvalues is performed following the methodology and formulation presented in [25]. The obtained oscillatory modes for the two scenarios described previously are disclosed in Table 2. For every oscillatory mode, the associated eigenvalue and the state variables are shown. For the inertia and damping values considered in Table 1, there are only two oscillatory modes related to the VSM electromechanical variables (phase, θ_{VSM} , and frequency, ω_{VSM}). Moreover, due to the PI effect, where initially arbitrary K_p and K_i gains have been used [$K_p = -1$ and $K_i = -30$ (these gains are negative based on the sign criteria used in Fig. 2)], the eigenvalues of the electromechanical modes of VSM with the supplementary controller diverge significantly from those of the ideal current-controlled VSM. This fact means that the resulting VSM dynamic response when the dc voltage regulation is considered is significantly distorted compared with that of the ideal current-controlled VSM. This issue should be fixed by calculating the optimum K_p and K_i gains, so that the dynamic response of both VSM schemes approaches as much as possible.

This study is extended in Fig. 3(a) and (b), where the locations in the complex S-plane of the eigenvalues related to the electromechanical modes of the ideal current-controlled VSM (without dc voltage supplementary controller) for different values of inertia constants, H and damping gains, K_d , are shown. Besides, Fig. 3(c) shows that the location of these eigenvalues is barely affected by the operating point defined in terms of the active power being processed in the system. Therefore, these values will be taken as targets for

FIGURE 3. (a) Ideal electromechanical eigenvalues location for $H = [2, 10]$ and $K_d = 200$. (b) Ideal electromechanical eigenvalues location for $H = 10$ and $K_d = [80, 400]$. (c) Ideal electromechanical eigenvalues location under battery charge/discharge power variation for $H = 10$ and $K_d = 200$.

tuning the gains of the supplementary controller. In this way, the influence of the supplementary control is minimized and the dynamic response of the dual-side VSM, whose control scheme is depicted in Fig. 2, provides the required ac-side inertia and damping as an ideal VSM.

B. CF DEFINITION FOR CONTROL TUNING AND OPTIMIZATION RESULTS

With the aim of calculating the optimum K_p and K_i gains, a CF to quantify the divergence between the ideal and dual-side VSM electromechanical eigenvalues is defined. By minimizing it, the dynamic response of both VSMs will be as close as possible. The proposed CF is given by (7), where n is the total number of electromechanical eigenvalues, Eig_i^* is the target value for every i th electromechanical eigenvalue [displayed in Fig. 3(a) and (b)] and Eig_i is the closest dual-side VSM

eigenvalue given by a specific K_p and K_i combination

$$\text{CF} = \sum_{i=1}^n |\text{Eig}_i - \text{Eig}_i^*|. \quad (7)$$

More detailed CFs could be considered, such as the one given by (8), where the normalized error between the real part of the targeted and obtained dual-side VSM eigenvalues as well as the damping terms (which are directly related to the cosine of the eigenvalue phases [21]) are used to quantify the dynamic performance difference between the ideal and dual-side VSMs. This approximation provides more accurate results. However, as it is shown in Sections IV and VI, the assessment given by (7) is good enough to facilitate an accurate parameter tuning while being very simple

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CF}_{\text{detailed}} = & \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\text{Re}\{\text{Eig}_i\} - \text{Re}\{\text{Eig}_i^*\}}{\text{Re}\{\text{Eig}_i^*\}} \right| + \dots \\ & \dots + \left| \cos(\angle \text{Eig}_i) - \cos(\angle \text{Eig}_i^*) \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In addition to minimizing the CF, it is also required to calculate the PI constants without exceeding a maximum predefined settling time, T_s , to reach the desired charge/discharge power reference of the battery systems. Otherwise, the transient time required to follow variations in the active power references of the dc/dc converters would take longer than expected. The latter can be done through the adjustment of the mode that is related to the dc bus voltage, using (9), where σ is the real part absolute value of the associated eigenvalue [26]

$$T_s = \frac{4}{\sigma}. \quad (9)$$

Considering the test case described in Table 1, a sweep has been realized for the PI constants, K_p and K_i , where the corresponding CF values are calculated for different H and K_d values. Fig. 4(a)–(c) shows the region with lowest CF values, considering a maximum settling time $T_s = 20$ s for different H and K_d values. These figures clearly illustrate the effect of the K_p and K_i gains in the eigenvalues through the CF value. By selecting the proper (K_p, K_i) pair that minimizes the CF, the dynamic performance of the dual-side VSM and the ideal VSM exhibit similar behavior, with minimal differences between them. Fig. 5(a) and (b) shows the influence of the maximum allowed settling time in the selection of the K_p and K_i gains. As T_s decreases, the range of suitable K_p and K_i values to minimize the CF is reduced and the minimum value of the CF that can be obtained increases. This means that a supplementary dc bus voltage regulator with faster response implies a higher perturbation of the dual-side VSM dynamic response, comparing with the ideal VSM. Therefore, a compromise must be obtained between the maximum T_s and the desired inertia and damping values requested to the VSM. In this work, a T_s of tens of seconds has been considered suitable, regarding the usual battery charging/discharging times [27].

FIGURE 4. Electromechanical eigenvalues location error, given by (7), for different K_p and K_i values to provide. (a) $H = 10$ and $K_d = 80$ with $T_s = 20$ s. (b) $H = 2$ and $K_d = 400$ with $T_s = 20$ s. (c) $H = 2$ and $K_d = 80$ with $T_s = 20$ s.

C. REAL-TIME TUNING SYSTEM BASED ON ANNS

The proposed methodology allows the offline calculation of the optimum (K_p, K_i) pairs for different VSM configuration parameters. Despite in this article only the inertia constant (H) and the damping gain (K_d) have been considered as variable, assuming the rest of parameters constant, other configuration parameters, such as the virtual impedance, the droop gain, k_w , or the maximum allowed settling time (T_s), among others, can be considered variable as well. The proposed methodology can be directly applied to additional variable parameters just including their corresponding sweeps.

The optimum (K_p, K_i) pairs for all the possible configuration values generate a resulting dataset that can be used to train a multilayer perceptron ANN [28] (see Fig. 6), which can be executed in real-time controllers [17] to provide the optimum tuning of the supplementary controller for any requested parameterization set. The ANN inputs are the desired dual-side VSM configuration parameter values. The ANN is

FIGURE 5. Electromechanical eigenvalues location error, given by (7), with: (a) maximum $T_s = 20$ s, $H = 10$, and $K_d = 400$; (b) Maximum $T_s = 10$ s, $H = 10$, and $K_d = 400$.

FIGURE 6. ANN scheme for GF controller.

capable of inferring causal nonlinear relationships between these inputs and the optimum (K_p, K_i) gains in real-time. Lookup tables (LUTs) can be also used to store the optimum (K_p, K_i) pairs for discrete combinations of the configuration parameters, in such a way that the optimum (K_p, K_i) pair for a desired parameterization of the VSM can be obtained through an interpolation method. However, the main advantage of using ANNs with respect to LUTs is their scalability and lower storage requirements, especially when the number of input parameters to be considered is high, since the LUT size increases exponentially with the number of dimensions.

In this work, two different configuration parameters have been considered for the ANN training; H and K_d . The parameter ranges and step size for the discretization are detailed in Table 3. The number of training sampled data points is 10^4 . The rest of parameters, included in Table 1, are constant and the maximum allowed settling time for the VSM active power dynamic response is also constant, $T_s = 20$ s. For each pair of

TABLE 3. Solution Space Considered for ANN Training

ANN input parameter	Parameter value range	Step size
H	[2, 10]	0.08 p.u.
K_d	[80, 400]	3.2 p.u.

FIGURE 7. (a) Ideal K_p for ANN training. (b) Ideal K_i for ANN training.
TABLE 4. GF ANN Features

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
N° hidden layers	4	Neurons hidden layer	70
Activation func.	Sigmoid	Batch size	8
Initialization	Glorot-uniform	Max. epochs	1000

configuration parameters (H , K_d), the optimum combination of gains (K_p , K_i) are calculated offline, as described in Sections III-A and III-B, and used as a dataset to train the ANN. This dataset, shown in Fig. 7(a) and (b), has been calculated with a parameter sweep step size of 0.03 p.u. and 0.043 p.u. for K_p and K_i , respectively. The main features of the resulting ANN, trained using the python KERAS library, are detailed in Table 4. It provides correct K_p and K_i parameter values for all the combinations of the configuration parameters H and K_d considered.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulation results have been obtained for the scheme illustrated in Fig. 1. The system is configured according to the

TABLE 5. Simulation Results Test Cases

Case	H	K_d	T_s	K_p	K_i
1	10	400	20 s	-0.47	-1.98
2	10	400	10 s	-1.1	-3.99
3	10	80	20 s	-0.1	-2.11
4	2	400	20 s	-0.72	-2.11
5	2	80	20 s	-0.1	-2.11

parameters included in Table 1. Three different BESS connected to the dc grid, each with a nominal power of 0.33 p.u., have been considered and the interface ac/dc converter makes use of the dual-side VSM.

Fig. 8 shows the active power that the VSM is injecting to the grid, the internal frequency of the VSM and the dc voltage in response to a grid frequency variation of -0.01 p.u., with a maximum rate of change of -2 Hz/s [29], that takes place at $t = 30$ s. The results include those obtained for the ideal VSM and the dual-side VSM for five distinct test cases characterized by varying values of H , K_d , and T_s (as presented in Table 5).

Initially, for the case I, the dual-side VSM performance is evaluated without any tuning process, using arbitrarily selected supplementary PI parameters ($K_p = -1$, $K_i = -30$). As shown in Fig. 8(a), the active power injected into the grid by the VSM exhibits significant deterioration under grid voltage frequency transients, compared to the ideal VSM performance. This highlights the necessity for a tuning process to optimize the dual-side VSM control. By applying the tuning methodology outlined in Section III, the optimal PI controller parameters have been determined, comprising the K_p and K_i gains, in this case for $T_s = 20$ s [see Fig. 8(a)–(c)]. The optimal PI parameters have also been calculated for the rest of test cases. It can be appreciated how, thanks to the proposed tuning method, the dual-side VSM dynamic response is as close as possible to that of the ideal VSM for all the test cases (see Fig. 8).

Among all the possible combinations of H and K_d within the margins defined in Table 3, the worst-case scenario, i.e., the one which provides the highest CF value, thus indicating the highest divergence between eigenvalues, has been computed resulting in that obtained when $H = 10$ and $K_d = 80$ (test case 3 in Table 5). It can be observed how, even in this case [see Fig. 8(g)–(i)], the transient response of the dual-side VSM approaches well that of the ideal VSM.

Fig. 8 also provides a clear assessment on how the dynamics of the VSM clearly depend on the VSM configuration parameters H and K_d . As K_d decreases, the oscillatory modes excited when the grid frequency variation takes place are less damped. Similarly, as H increases, the VSM speed varies more slowly. This is common in all VSM implementations.

Fig. 9 shows the dual-side VSM active power and internal frequency for the test case 1 ($H = 10$ s, $K_d = 400$, $T_s = 20$ s) and test case 2 ($H = 10$ s, $K_d = 400$, $T_s = 10$ s) under:

FIGURE 8. VSM active power injected to the ac grid for both the dual-side VSM [case 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 (see Table 5)] and the ideal VSM, under a grid frequency transition of 1%. (a)–(c) Case 1 with and without PI tuning. (d)–(f) Case 2. (g)–(i) Case 3. (j)–(l) Case 4. (m)–(o) Case 5.

- 1) a grid frequency variation of -0.01 p.u. at $t = 30$ s;
- 2) a grid frequency variation of 0.01 p.u. at $t = 50$ s;
- 3) a grid voltage phase variation of 5° at $t = 60$ s (as requested in National Grid Code GC0137 [29]).

As expected, as T_s decreases, the impact of the supplementary PI controller on the dynamics of the dual-side VSM becomes more evident, making this dynamic performance differ slightly more from that of the ideal VSM.

Figs. 8 and 9 also illustrates the combined effect of $V_{dc}-f$ and $V_{dc}-P$ droop characteristics, given by (4) and (5), respectively, that results in the primary frequency response of the control scheme described in Section II. Taking as a reference

the results of test case 1, it can be appreciated how when the grid frequency changes at $t = 30$ s, the resulting active power and internal frequency of the VSM varies accordingly [see Fig. 8(a) and (b), respectively]. As the internal frequency of the VSM changes, so does the voltage reference for the PI supplementary controller as defined by the $V_{dc}-f$ droop in (4). As the real dc bus voltage follows this reference [see Fig. 8(c)], the power reference of the dc/dc converter changes according to the $V_{dc}-P$ droop given by (5), thus providing the required power for the primary frequency support.

Fig. 10 shows the response of the system under a power set-point change of one of the BESS (BESS-3) connected to

FIGURE 9. (a) VSM active power injected to the ac grid for $T_s = 10$ s, $T_s = 20$ s, and the ideal scenario. (b) VSM frequency ω_{VSM} .

FIGURE 10. (a) BESS-3 absorbed active power for $T_s = 20$ s and $T_s = 10$ s. (b) Dc bus voltage for $T_s = 20$ s and $T_s = 10$ s. (c) VSM active power injected to the ac grid for $T_s = 10$ s and $T_s = 20$ s.

FIGURE 11. Position of electromechanical poles under SCR variation.

FIGURE 12. Optimum K_p and K_i values under SCR variation for $H = 10$ and $K_d = 200$.

the dc grid, while the other two BESS systems (BESS-1 and BESS-2) are absorbing an active power of 0.165 p.u. each. Fig. 10(a) shows the power that the dc/dc converter connected to the BESS-3 is absorbing from the dc grid for the test cases 1 and 2. As the power set-point changes, the real power absorbed by the dc/dc does accordingly. Consequently, the dc voltage also changes [see Fig. 10(b)] and the supplementary PI controller takes over and change the active power injected by the VSM to the grid [see Fig. 10(c)]. The dynamic response of the system is defined according to the T_s specified at every test case.

V. ROBUSTNESS DISCUSSION

A study has been conducted to determine the robustness of the proposed parameter tuning method under variations in the grid strength or uncertainties in the system parameters.

A. GRID STRENGTH VARIATION

The optimum K_p and K_i values have been obtained for different short-circuit ratios (SCRs) in the range [2, 15]. First, the electromechanical pole variation of the ideal VSM is analyzed. As can be seen in Fig. 3, for $K_d = 80$, $H = 10$, and $\text{SCR} = 15$, there are two conjugate electromechanical poles. If the SCR is modified, these poles are shifted, as shown in Fig. 11. Due to this movement, the optimum values of K_p and K_i can vary with respect to the case of a strong grid ($\text{SCR} = 15$), as can be seen in Fig. 12.

The study has been repeated for a different inertia and damping configuration, specifically $H = 10$ and $K_d = 80$,

FIGURE 13. Optimum K_p and K_i under SCR variation for $H = 10$ and $K_d = 80$.

FIGURE 14. Position of electromechanical poles under $\pm 10\%$ L_f variation.

which represents the case study with the highest performance deviation between the ideal and dual-side VSMs, as indicated in Section IV. As shown in Fig. 13, the optimum values of K_p and K_i are also affected by the SCR values. However, these variations are relatively minor and do not significantly compromise the dual-side VSM's dynamic performance if the K_p and K_i values obtained with SCR=15 are used.

In addition, as mentioned in Section III-C, the proposed ANN can be redesigned to include additional inputs. Among these inputs, the SCR could be considered to optimize the K_p and K_i values for different grid impedance values. For this type of ANN design, an SCR estimator, such as the one presented in [30], would be required.

B. SYSTEM PARAMETER UNCERTAINTIES

The effect of $\pm 10\%$ deviations in the VSM output filter inductance or the dc bus capacitance on the position of the electromechanical poles has been studied. As shown in Table 1, the VSM output inductance is rated at 0.15 p.u. With this value, the electromechanical poles are located at $-4.4624 \pm 5.2428i$ for $H = 10$ and $K_d = 200$ [see Fig. 3(a)]. There is another pole at -10.472 , but it is related to the current control. In Fig. 14, under $\pm 10\%$ output inductance variation, the electromechanical poles do not move; only the pole related to the current controller is shifted. Therefore, this uncertainty does not affect the emulated inertia or damping.

On the other hand, the nominal capacitance of the dc bus is 10.2 mF. As shown in Fig. 15, the electromechanical poles do not move under a capacitance variation of $\pm 10\%$. As a

FIGURE 15. Position of electromechanical poles under $\pm 10\%$ C_{dc} variation.

TABLE 6. Experimental Setup Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Nominal power, P	625W	V_{LL-rms}	200V
Grid SCR	153	L_{VSM}	0.25 p.u.
R_{VSM}	0.05 p.u.	L_f	0.05 p.u.
R_f	$6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ p.u.	C_f	0.045 p.u.
R_d	0.08 p.u.	L_g	$6.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ p.u.
R_g	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ p.u.	K_w	20 p.u.
H	[2, 10] p.u.	k_d	[80, 400] p.u.
V_{dc}	300V	C_{dc}	3.3mF
V_{bat}	96V	$L_{dc/dc}$	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ p.u.
$K_{droop-dc}$	10 p.u.		

result, the optimum values of K_p and K_i are not affected by uncertainties in the system parameters.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 16 shows a schematic of the experimental setup which has been used to validate the dual-side GF controller and the proposed tuning method. The dc/dc and dc/ac power stages have been built using Dutt INF-50 power inverters. The BESS is emulated using a Mean Well BIC-2200-96 bidirectional 96 Vdc power supply. For the three-phase ac grid, a Pacific Power 320-AMX bidirectional power supply is used. The connection between the dc/ac stage and the grid is done through an LCL circuit, including a damping resistor R_d to prevent resonance issues. The controller for both power stages has been implemented in a National Instruments cRIO-9040, which consists of an Intel Atom CPU, an FPGA Kintex and modules for high-speed digital outputs and analog inputs. For the dual-side VSM, the controller depicted in Fig. 2, except for the current controller, and the ANN are executed in the CPU at 1 kHz. The current controller is executed in the FPGA at 10 kHz. Probes and passive elements are off-the-shelf components.

The main parameters of the setup are summed up in Table 6. These parameters have been considered for the tuning process described in Section III. The optimum values obtained for K_p and K_i are similar to the ones shown in Table 5 for every test case. These test cases are validated considering two different transient states to study the VSM dynamic response:

FIGURE 16. Experimental setup for validating the controller performance.

FIGURE 17. Experimental results under a power setpoint step for Case 1: (a) Active power. (b) DC bus voltage.

FIGURE 18. Experimental results under a power setpoint step for Case 2: (a) Active power. (b) DC bus voltage.

1) a BESS power setpoint step and 2) a grid frequency step. For the grid frequency step, both positive and negative frequency steps have been tested, but only the latter is shown due to the symmetrical behavior of the dual-side VSM controller. Finally, the computational load of the ANN in real-time controllers is discussed.

A. BESS POWER SETPOINT STEP

As the behaviour of the dual-side VSM controller under a BESS power step depends mainly on T_s , case 1 ($T_s = 20$ s) and case 2 ($T_s = 10$ s) are compared with each other. The results are shown in Figs. 17 and 18, respectively. In both cases, the VSM is initially injecting an active power of -0.2 p.u. At $t = 1$ s, a BESS power step of -0.4 p.u. is applied. The GF controller with lower T_s has higher active power dynamics, which is also translated into the dc bus voltage transient. The simulated signals have been superimposed on the experimental ones to show that the controller response is as expected.

B. GRID FREQUENCY STEP

Under a grid frequency step, the system dynamics will mainly depend on the inertia H and damping K_d coefficients. Fig. 19 shows the active power, internal frequency of the VSM and dc bus voltage transient when the different test cases face a -0.01 p.u. frequency step. Simulated and experimental signals are superimposed, showing similar performance.

Case 1 [see Fig. 19(a)] and case 2 [see Fig. 19(b)] show a nearly identical transient behaviour during these tests. However, as commented in Section III, as case 2 has a lower T_s , it provides a closer performance to an ideal VSM.

Fig. 19(c) shows an undamped response under the frequency step. This behavior reflects the high inertia and low damping coefficients used. The oscillation leads to a transient saturation of the converter output voltage during the peak power, impacting the quality of the signal. On the other hand, Fig. 19(d) and Fig. 19(e) shows the response when the system inertia is reduced to 2 s. In this case, the transient is faster and the damping is considerably improved, especially in Fig. 19(d) where $K_d = 400$.

Finally, the energy required to emulate inertia in the frequency step considered has been calculated for all the cases. This energy is influenced by the parameters H and K_d . For example, using $K_d = 400$ and considering the experimental setup parameters (see Table 6), the energy requirements are 100 J for $H = 2$ and 500 J for $H = 10$, respectively. Notably, these energy requirements are relatively low for a system with a nominal power of 625W.

FIGURE 19. Active power, grid frequency and dc bus voltage under a grid frequency step of -0.01 p.u. (a) Case 1. (b) Case 2. (c) Case 3. (d) Case 4. (e) Case 5.

C. DISCUSSION ON THE FEASIBILITY OF EXECUTING THE ANN IN REAL-TIME

The ANN has been integrated into the VSM controller, operating with a time step of 1 ms in the real-time control system cRIO-9040. To illustrate the computational burden of the ANN and its real-time feasibility, a dedicated task was created containing only the ANN. The computation time was measured over 20 s (20 000 time steps) and is presented in Fig. 20. As shown, the maximum computation time required by the ANN is 300 μ s. As a result, it can be concluded that real-time processors, such as the cRIO-9040 or the Zynq-7000 family, an embedded hardware used to control power converters [31],

are capable of running the ANN at control frequencies higher than 1 kHz. In this way, the time constraints to adjust inertia or damping, as requested by the grid operator, are met, since they are usually in the order of seconds.

VII. CONCLUSION

A novel tuning method, based on small signal analysis, has been presented to adjust the configuration parameters of dual-side GF controllers in charge of regulating the voltage at both sides, ac and dc, of the VSM. These controllers use the available stored energy in the grid to provide this double regulation. In this way, in hybrid ac/dc grids, it is possible to provide

FIGURE 20. Computational burden required by the ANN in the CPU of cRIO.

auxiliary services to the ac grid, supported by the BESS systems connected to the dc grid, through an ac/dc interface implemented by a dual-side VSM. In this article, through the proposed tuning method, this dual-side VSM will present a similar electromechanical dynamic performance with respect to an ideal VSM (where the dc bus voltage is not regulated).

A CF based on the electromechanical poles of the system which compares the pole location of an ideal VSM with respect to a dual-side VSM is proposed to be minimized. Specifically, through this CF, the K_p and K_i constants of the supplementary PI controller that regulates the dc bus voltage have been tuned with the aim of obtaining a dual-side VSM performance close to the ideal one.

The proposed method has been validated through several simulation and experimental results under different test cases where different emulated inertia, damping, and active power settling time have been considered.

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ANGEL PEREZ-BASANTE received the B.Eng. degree in telecommunications engineering from the University of Valladolid, Valladolid, Spain, in 2006, the M.Eng. degree in electronic systems engineering from the Technical University of Madrid, Madrid, Spain, in 2012, and the Ph.D. degree in advanced electronic systems engineering from the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Bilba, Spain, in 2017.

Since 2017, he has been a Researcher with Tecnalia Research and Innovation in the Energy, Climate and Urban Transition Unit. From 2012 to 2016, he was a Ph.D. Student in the Applied Electronics Research Team (APERT), University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) in collaboration with Tecnalia Research and Innovation. In addition, from September 2015 to December 2015, he was a Visiting Researcher with the Chair of Power Electronics of the Christian Albrechts University, Kiel, Germany. His research interests include multilevel converters, advanced modulation and control strategies, power semiconductor reliability, and the stability analysis of electrical systems.

ASIER GIL DE MURO received the M.Sc. degree in electrical engineering from the School of Engineering, University of the Basque Country, Bilbao, Spain, in 1998.

Since 1999, he has been a Researcher and Project Manager with the Energy and Environmental Division of TECNALIA in the smart grid area, working in projects dealing with power electronics equipment, design and developing of grid interconnected power devices and stability analysis of the converters in the time and frequency domain. He is also involved in projects related with the control of Microgrids and active distribution. He is mainly related with the hardware and firmware design of testing prototypes and the control algorithms and stability. He participated in several European funded projects (DGFACTS, DINEMO, FENIX, MICROGRIDS, MORE-MICROGRIDS, IGREENGRID, etc.). He has been also a Professor with the School of Engineering, University of the Basque Country in the electronic and telecommunication department.

ANDER ORDONO received the B.E. degree in renewable energies engineering from the University of the Basque Country, Bilbao, Spain, in 2015, and the M.E. degree in power electronics and energy from Mondragon University, Mondragon, Spain, in 2017. He is currently working toward the Ph.D. degree in electrical energy systems with the University of the Basque Country.

From 2017 to 2022, he was a Researcher with Automation and Control Unit, Tekniker, Gipuzkoa, Spain. In 2022, he joined the Electrical Department of the University of the Basque Country. His research interests include the modeling, analysis, and control of grid-connected converters.

SALVADOR CEBALLOS received the M.S. degree in physics from the University of Cantabria, Santander, Spain, in 2001, and the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in electronic engineering from the University of the Basque Country, Bilbao, Spain, in 2002 and 2008, respectively.

Since 2002, he has been with Tecnalia Research and Innovation, Derio, Spain, where he is currently a Principal Researcher in the Energy, Climate, and Urban Transition Unit. His research interests include multilevel converters for high- and medium-voltage applications, fault-tolerant power electronic topologies, renewable energy systems and power systems with high penetration of power converters.

ENEKO UNAMUNO received the M.Sc. in energy and power electronics and international Ph.D. degree in mechanical and electrical energy engineering from Mondragon Unibertsitatea, Mondragón, Spain, in 2014 and 2017, respectively.

From March to May 2017, he was a Visiting Researcher with the Department of Engineering Cybernetics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway. He is currently the Researcher and Lecturer with the Faculty of Engineering, Mondragon Unibertsitatea. His research interests include the development of modeling, analysis, control, and energy management techniques for ac, dc, and hybrid ac/dc power systems with a large presence of electronic power converters, and the integration of distributed, renewable energy-based generation, and energy storage systems into the grid.

JON ANDONI BARRENA received the M.Sc. degree (with distinction) in electrical power engineering from the University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology, Manchester, U.K., in 2001, and the Ph.D. degree in power electronics from Mondragon University, Mondragon, Spain, in 2007.

Since 2001, he has been a Full Professor with Mondragon University, where he has been the Head Researcher of the Electrical Energy Research Line since 2012. He has authored or coauthored more than 30 papers published in international journals with impact factor, more than 30 papers published in international and national conferences, and coauthored one book and two book chapters and two patents. He has successfully supervised 16 Ph.D.'s and is currently supervising one Ph.D. student. His research interests include power electronics, grid quality, distributed generation, and industrial drive systems.